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Effect of Exogenous Application of Ascorbic Acid (Vitamin C) on Proline Accumulation, Productivity and Quality of Sugarcane under Salt Stress

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Abstract

The field study was carried out at Sugarcane Research Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Cuddalore by using the sugarcane variety CoC 25 during the period of 2015-2018. This study was conducted to determine the sett treatment and a foliar spray of ascorbic acid on physiology, yield and quality parameters of sugarcane under saline water irrigated condition in two plant crops and one ratoon crop. Results of pooled mean data of two plant crops and ratoon crop showed that sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th days after planting showed maximum germination of 83% and 85% , tiller population of 1,42,480/ha and 1,45,060/ha, millable cane of 1,29,880/ha and 1,31,180/ha, leaf area of 727.90 cm² and 737.15 cm², leaf area index of 3.85 and 3.88 , total chlorophyll of 2.273 mg/g and 2.265 mg/g, proline content of 325 µg/g and 320 µg/g, cane length of 202.42 cm and 204.20 cm, cane girth of 2.70cm and 2.72cm in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The same treatment significantly registered the maximum cane yield of 124.60 t/ha and 125.71 t/ha and sugar yield of 14.04 t/ha and 14.12 t/ha, CCS% of 11.32 % and 11.36%, net income of Rs.1,73,850 and Rs.1,76,635 and B: C ratio of 1.96 and 1.98 both in plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Keywords: Sugarcane, ascorbic acid, proline, salinity, physiology, quality

Introduction

Sugarcane (*Saccharum* sp.) is a phenomenal plant species growing in tropical and subtropical regions (Rao *et al.*, 2015). The significance of stalk has additionally expanded as of late for its wide use in enterprises as a crude material for sugar, liquor, acidic acid, butanol, paper and animal feed (Sengar *et al.*, 2011). The sugarcane being a glycophyte (salt vulnerable), shows harmful indications including low spout development, nourishing irregularity and low profitability particularly sugar content when developed in the salt-influenced soils. Along these lines, the advancement of stress-open minded harvests will be enormously favorable for present-day agribusiness in regions that are inclined to such stress. The identification of salt tolerant parents and their cross combinations that could yielded higher proportion of tolerant genotypes is most necessary phenomenon. Ion homeostasis, osmoregulation, antioxidant and hormonal systems are some of the defense mechanisms that help halophytic species to cope up the saline conditions. Then again, glycophytic species are helpless to salt pressure, since they show decreased leaf development, chlorophyll substance and represent the toxic damages, *i.e.*, shrinking, chlorosis, necrosis, leaf burn and senescence (Suriyan Cha-um *et al.*, 2012). In excess of 45 million hectares (M ha) of inundated land records to 20% of all-out land have been harmed by salt

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worldwide and 1M ha are removed from cultivation every year because of high saltiness levels (Munns and Tester 2008).

A variety of salts present in the soil that are immediately broken down in the water to create harmful particles, particularly sodium particles (Na^+). Sodium (Na^+) consumed by root tissues and moved to the over the ground plant part through the xylem vascular tissues. Sodium particle (Na^+) is notable for adversely influencing plant development and improvement before plant cell demise. Saltiness, a genuine natural issue influences the development and improvement of the majority of the plants all through the globe (Ahanger *et al.*, 2014, Hameed *et al.*, 2014 and Wu *et al.*, 2014). A high salt level in the soil causes a few unfavorable impacts *viz.*, hyper-osmolality, particle disequilibrium supplement irregularity and creation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Every one of these retards the plant development through molecular damage as well as hampers numerous cell procedures, for example, photosynthesis, respiration and the plasma membrane function (Porcel *et al.*, 2012 and Sarwat *et al.*, 2016). NaCl is liable for both hyper ionic and hyperosmotic worry in plants, and its expanded collection in the soil changes its essential structure and results in diminishing soil porosity thus, decreasing soil air circulation and conductance of water (Porcel *et al.*, 2012). Ascorbic acid (AA) is one of the most widely studied antioxidants that have been detected in the majority of plant cell types, organelles and apoplast (Borland *et al.*, 2006). Endogenous ascorbic acid can be expanded by exogenous use of ascorbic acid as a foliar spray or as seed priming through the rooting medium. Regardless of its job in rummaging reactive oxygen species, ascorbic acid is likewise associated with managing photosynthetic limits by controlling stomatal development.

A fundamental role of ascorbic acid is providing defense system in plant and protecting the metabolic processes against H_2O_2 and other toxic derivatives of oxygen. It responds non-enzymatically with superoxide, hydrogen peroxide, and singlet oxygen (Pourcel *et al.*, 2007) and goes about as an essential substrate in the cyclic pathway for the enzymatic detoxification of hydrogen peroxide; thus, it has a significant role in the activation of various biological mechanisms and plant defense. It is implied as one of the most productive growth regulators against abiotic stresses and its cellular levels are correlated with the activation of complex biological defense mechanisms. It has also used to counteract the adverse effects of salt stress in many crop plants (Khan *et al.*, 2010). Salt-instigated unfavorable impacts could be decreased altogether with the exogenous use of ascorbic acid and increment the development and yield of plants (Ejaz *et al.*, 2012). In recent years, the involvement of ascorbic acid in response to abiotic stresses has come into light. Several studies support a major role of ascorbic acid in plant adaptation to the changing environment and induce plant tolerance to various abiotic stresses including elevated NaCl (Abbasi *et al.*, 2015). It is a very much watched actuality that ascorbic acid conceivably produces a wide exhibit of metabolic reactions in plants and furthermore influences plant water relations (Hayat *et al.*, 2010). It controls cell division and cell development, goes about as a cofactor of numerous proteins, regulates plant sense and is engaged with photosynthesis, hormone biosynthesis and regeneration of antioxidants (Gallie, 2013 and Lisko *et al.*, 2014). In general, the impacts of ascorbic acid in relieving the unfavourable effects of salt pressure have been portrayed to the initiation of a portion of the enzymatic responses. Hence in this study, an attempt has been made to ascertain the salinity effect and its mitigation with ascorbic acid in sugarcane cultivar.

Materials and Methods

The field experiment was conducted during the early season of 2015-18 in Sugarcane Research Station at Cuddalore to alleviate the salinity stress by sett treatment and foliar spray of Ascorbic Acid. The first year plant crop was raised during 2015-16 and it was ratooned during 2016-17. At the same time the second plant was raised during 2017-2018. The Soils pH is 7.90 and EC is 0.40 dsm^{-1} and the water pH is 7.94 and water EC is 3.58 dsm^{-1} . Salt status in water content is HCO_3 of 7.98 meq./100ml, Cl of 18.85 meq./100ml, SO_4 of 2.98 meq./100ml, Ca of 6.43 meq./100ml, Mg of 6.69 meq./100ml, Na of 10.49 meq./100ml, K of 0.2 meq./100ml, SAR of 7.98 meq./100ml, Mg:Ca of 2.32 meq./100ml. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with five replications. The treatments constituted of T_1 –Control, T_2 –Foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP, T_3 –Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP,

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T₄ – Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l. The data on germination, population of tillers, millable canes, plant height, number of nodes per plant, length of internodes, leaf area, leaf area index, total chlorophyll, proline content, cane length, cane girth, commercial cane sugar per cent, cane yield, sugar yield and economics containing cost of cultivation, gross income, net income and benefit cost ratio were documented in two plant crops and one ratoon crop. The pooled mean of two plant crops and ratoon crop were presented in Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4.

The data on various observations recorded were analyzed statistically by adopting the procedures of Gomez and Gomez (1984).

Results and Discussion

Growth parameters

The effect of ascorbic acid on mean germination percentage of both plant and ratoon crops under salinity condition are presented in Table 1. Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) significantly registered the maximum mean germination percentage of 83% and 85% in plant crop I and plant crop II respectively. The influence of ascorbic acid as sett treatment and foliar application at 45th days after planting on CoC 25 exerts significant variations at all growth stages compare to control. The effect of ascorbic acid on mean tiller population of both plant and ratoon crops under salinity condition are presented in Table 1. Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP fundamentally recorded the greatest mean tiller population of 1,42,480/ha and 1,45,060/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The foliar spray of 1mM (0.2g/l) ascorbic acid at 45th DAP (T₄) remains next with the mean tiller population of 1,35,480/ha and 1,41,240/ha in ratoon crop respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the base mean tiller population of 1,25,670/ha and 1,26,670/ha in plant and ratoon crops respectively.

The effect of ascorbic acid on the millable cane population of plant and ratoon crops under salinity is presented in Table 1. Among the treatments, sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) altogether enrolled the higher mean millable cane of 1,29,880/ha and 1,31,187/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The treatment T₄ (foliar spray of 0.2g/l ascorbic acid at 45th DAP) remains next with a population of 1,26,760/ha and 1,23,890/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. This was due to better uptake of nutrients and production of economic shoots. There was a significant difference between the treatments with respect to tiller population. However it was comparable with the application of T₂ treatment (sett treatment of ascorbic acid 0.2g/l). The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean millable cane population of 1,16,900/ha in plant and 1,17,650/ha in ratoon crop respectively.

Among the evaluated treatments the sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) registered significantly higher mean plant height of 356 cm and 358 cm in plant and ratoon crops respectively and it is followed by a foliar spray of ascorbic acid 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₄) with a plant height of 337 cm and 348 cm in plant and ratoon crops respectively. It was comparable with the control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean plant height of 309 cm and 311cm in plant and ratoon crops respectively. This study also found that salt stress reduced the plant growth due to the reduction of photosynthesis effects. This may due to stomatal closure and reduction of water entry into the plant ultimately caused a reduction in plant height (Table 1).

The effect of ascorbic acid on the number of nodes of plant and ratoon crops under salinity is presented in Table 1. Among the treatments, sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) observed significantly higher mean number of nodes of 25 and 24 in plant and ratoon crops respectively and it is on par with a foliar spray of 0.2g/l ascorbic acid at 45th DAP (T₄) with 24 and 22 in plant and ratoon crops respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean number of nodes of 19 and 18 in plant and ratoon crops respectively.

The effect of ascorbic acid on length of the internode of plant and ratoon crops under salinity is presented in Table 1. Among the treatments, sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic

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acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) significantly registered the maximum mean internode length of 10.11cm and 10.32 cm in plant and ratoon crops respectively and it is on par with foliar spray of 0.2g/l ascorbic acid at 45th DAP (T₄) with 8.70 cm and 9.08 cm in plant and ratoon crops respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean internode length of 6.17 cm and 6.24 cm in plant and ratoon crops respectively.

Physiological parameters

The effect of ascorbic acid on leaf area of both plant and ratoon crops under salinity condition are presented in Table 2. Among the evaluated treatments, the sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) recorded significantly higher the maximum mean leaf area of 727.90 cm² and 737.15 cm² in plant and ratoon crop respectively. Leaf area index also recorded maximum of 3.85 and 3.88 in plant and ratoon crop respectively in the same treatment. Leaf area index is an important sugarcane yield attributing indices since sugarcane has high leaf area index and a high photosynthetic efficiency under ample sunlight, compare to any other crops. Variation in growth and productivity is closely related to the amount of intercepted radiation, largely determined by leaf area index. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean leaf area of 560.56 cm² and 562.68 cm² and leaf area index of 3.11 and 3.13 in plant and ratoon crop respectively (Table 2).

Among the evaluated treatments the sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) significantly registered the maximum mean total chlorophyll content of 2.292 mg/g and 2.265 mg/g in plant and ratoon crops respectively and it is on par with foliar spray of ascorbic acid 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₄) with 2.112 mg/g and 2.157 mg/g of chlorophyll in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean total chlorophyll content of 1.752 mg/g and 1.753 mg/g in plant and ratoon crops respectively. In a recent study, Azzedine *et al.* (2011) reported that the application of vitamin C was effective to mitigate the adverse effect of salt stress on plant growth due to increased leaf area, improved chlorophyll contents, enhanced protein accumulation and decreased H₂O₂ content.

Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) significantly registered the maximum mean proline content of 325 and 320 µg/g of tissue in plant and ratoon crops respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean proline content of 288 and 290 µg/g of tissue in plant and ratoon crops respectively. The proline content of sugarcane plants showed an increasing trend after ascorbic acid application under salinity condition. The accumulation of proline associated with stress might serve as a compatible solute in order to maintain the osmotic balance and allow the plants to acclimatize to unfavorable environment. Besides it also acts as a component of the antioxidative defense system rather than an osmotic adjustment mediator.

Yield parameters

The effect of ascorbic acid on cane length of plant and ratoon crops under salinity is presented in Table 3. Among the treatments, sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) significantly registered the maximum mean cane length of 202.42 cm and 204.20 cm in plant and ratoon crops respectively. The maximum cane length obtained in this treatment might be due to ascorbic acid (Vitamin C) required by the seedlings for effective utilization of various crop impact resources for its better utilization towards root shoot growth and reflected upon enhanced cane height. The minimum cane length of 161.21 cm and 165.20 cm was recorded in plant and ratoon crop respectively in T₁- control.

Among the treatments, sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) significantly registered the maximum mean cane girth of 2.70 cm and 2.72 cm in plant and ratoon crops respectively. The sugarcane crop would have utilize the resources at the maximum extant for enhanced productivity of photosynthetic assimilates in terms of sucrose at the source region and its effective accumulation in cane stalk, the sink region and it might be the probable reason for the enhanced values of

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varied yield components with this treatment. The minimum cane girth (2.12 cm and 2.20 cm) resulted with control (T₁).

The effect of ascorbic acid on cane yield of both plant and ratoon crops under salinity condition are presented in Table 3. Among the evaluated treatments, the sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) significantly registered the maximum mean cane yield of 124.60 t/ha and 125.71 t/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The yield was found to be progressively increased with sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP, the crop growth period under salinity condition uptake of nutrients get reduced, by application of ascorbic acid might have favored the faster cell division and cell elongation which ultimately resulted in higher tiller production and yield. The plant growth is also improved by the ability of the plant to uptake and receives more nutrients. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean cane yield of 101.60 t/ha and 105.02 t/ha in plant and ratoon crops respectively.

Among the treatments, sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) significantly registered the maximum mean commercial cane sugar of 11.32 % and 11.36 % in plant and ratoon crops respectively. Being the juice quality of sugarcane is a dependent genetic factor of cane cultivars, the significant increase could not be attributed. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean commercial cane sugar of 10.97 % and 10.96 % in plant and ratoon crops respectively.

The effect of ascorbic acid on sugar yield of both plant and ratoon crops under salinity condition are presented in Table 3. Among the evaluated treatments the sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) significantly registered the maximum mean sugar yield of 14.04 t/ha and 14.12 t/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean sugar yield 11.19 t/ha and 11.24 t/ha in plant and ratoon crops respectively.

The economics of sugarcane was worked out after harvest among the treatments, the sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP (T₃) recorded the maximum gross income of Rs.3,53,365 and Rs.3,56,485, net income of Rs.1,73,850 and Rs.1,76,635 and B:C ratio of 1.96 and 1.98 both in plant and ratoon crop respectively (Table 4).

Conclusion

Plant growth regulators (vitamin C) ascorbic acid solution increased yield and quality of sugarcane under salinity condition. Based on the present study findings, sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l and foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th days after planting was highly effective in overcoming the adverse effects of salinity stress through enhancing the overall physiological efficiency of the crop and enhancing the yield, quality and yield attributes characters of sugarcane variety CoC (SC) 25 both plant and ratoon crops. Sett treatment of 0.2g/l ascorbic acid and foliar spray of 0.2g/l ascorbic acid at 45th days after planting registered significantly maximum mean values of varied physiological and growth parameters in plant and ratoon crop viz., germination of 83% and 85% plant crop I and plant crop II respectively, tiller population of 1,42,480/ha and 1,45,060/ha, millable cane of 1,29,880/ha and 1,31,180/ha, leaf area of 727.90 cm² and 737.15 cm², leaf area index of 3.85 and 3.88, total chlorophyll of 2.273 mg/g and 2.265 mg/g, proline content of 325 µg/g and 320 µg/g, cane length of 202.42 cm and 204.20 cm, cane girth of 2.70cm and 2.72cm both plant and ratoon crop.

The same treatment significantly registered the maximum cane yield of 124.60 t/ha and 125.71 t/ha and sugar yield of 14.04 t/ha and 14.12 t/ha, CCS% of 11.32 % and 11.36%, net income of Rs.1,73,850 and Rs.1,76,635 and B: C ratio of 1.96 and 1.98 both in plant and ratoon crop respectively. By improving of the key biochemical attributes essential for the growth and better establishment of crop under salinity condition, the above treatments resulted with maximum values of varied growth, yield parameters and the productivity of sugarcane compare to saline water irrigated condition.

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Fig 1. Effect of ascorbic acid on growth parameters of sugarcane under saline water irrigated situations at tillering stage

Fig2. Effect of ascorbic acid application on yield of sugarcane under saline water irrigated situations at harvest stage

CONTROL

T₃

Reference

- i Abbasi, M., and E. Faghani. 2015. Role of salicylic acid and ascorbic acid in the alleviation of salinity stress in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *J. Bio. & Env. Sci.*, 6: (2) 107-113.
- ii Ahanger, M.A., A. Hashem, Abd Allah EF and P. Ahmad. 2014. Arbuscular mycorrhiza in crop improvement under environmental stress. In: Ahmad P, Rasool S. (Eds.), *Emerging Technologies and Management of Crop Stress Tolerance*. 2: 69-95.
- iii Azzedine, Hocine Gherroucha and Mebarek Baka. 2011. Improvement of salt tolerance in durum wheat by ascorbic acid application. *Journal of Stress Physiology & Biochemistry*, Vol. 7 No. 1, pp. 27-37 ISSN 1997-0838.

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- iv Borland, A., S. Elliott, S. Patterson, T. Taybi, J. Cushman, B. Pater and J. Barnes. 2006. Are the metabolic components of crassulacean acid metabolism up-regulated in response to an increase in oxidative burden? *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 57: 319-328.
- v Ejaz, B., Z.A. Sajid and F. Aftab. 2012. Effect of exogenous application of ascorbic acid on antioxidant enzyme activities, proline contents, and growth parameters of *Saccharum spp.* hybrid cv. HSF-240 under salt stress. *Turkish Journal of Biology*, 36: 630-640.
- vi Gallie, D.R. 2013. The role of L-ascorbic acid recycling in responding to environmental stress and in promoting plant growth. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 64 (2): 433-443.
- vii Hameed, A., E. Dilfuza, E.F. AbdAllah, A. Hashem, A. Kumar and P. Ahmad. 2014. Salinity stress and arbuscularmycorrhizal symbiosis in plants. In: M. Miransari (Ed.), *Use of Microbes for the Alleviation of Soil Stresses*, Springer Science+Business Media, New York. 1. 139-159.
- viii Hayat, Q., S. Hayat, M. Irfan and A. Ahmad. 2010. Effect of exogenous salicylic acid under changing environment: a review. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 68 (1): 14–25.
- ix Khan, A., I. Iqbal, A. Shah, H. Nawaz, F. Ahmad and M. Ibrahim. 2010. Alleviation of adverse effects of salt stress in brassica (*Brassica campestris*) by pre-sowing seed treatment with ascorbic acid. *American-Eurasian Journal of Agricultural & Environmental Sciences*, 7: 557-560.
- x Lisko, K.A., S.I. Aboobucker, R. Torres and A. Lorence. 2014. Engineering elevated vitamin C in plants to improve their nutritional content, growth, and tolerance to abiotic stress. *Recent Advances in Phytochemistry*, Springer. 109-128.
- xi Munns, R and M. Tester. 2008. Mechanisms of salinity tolerance. *Annu. Rev. Plant Biol.*, 59:651–681.
- xii Porcel, R., R. Aroca and J.M. RuizLozano. 2012. Salinity stress alleviation using arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi - A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 32: 181–200.
- xiii Pourcel, L., J.M. Routaboul, V. Cheynier, L. Lepiniec and I. Debeaujon. 2007. Flavonoid oxidation in plants: From biochemical properties to physiological functions. *Trends in Plant Science*, 12: 29-36.
- xiv Rao, V.P., R.S. Sengar, S. Singh and V. Sharma. 2015. Molecular and metabolic perspectives of sugarcane under salinity stress pressure. *Progressive Agriculture*, 15 (1): 77-84.
- xv Sarwat, M., A. Hashem, M.A. Ahanger, E.F. Abd_Allah, A.A. Alqarawi, M.N. Alyemeni and P. Ahmad. 2016. Mitigation of NaCl Stress by Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi through the modulation of osmolytes, antioxidants and secondary metabolites in Mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.). *Frontiers in Plant science*, 7: 869.
- xvi Sengar, R.S., K. Sengar and S.K. Garg. 2011. Biotechnological approaches for high sugarcane yield. *Plant Sciences Feed*, 1: 7.
- xvii Suriyan Cha-um, S. Chuencharoen, C. Mongkolsiriwatana, M. Ashraf and C. Kirdmanee. 2012. Screening sugarcane (*Saccharum sp.*) genotypes for salt tolerance using multivariate cluster analysis. *Plant cell, Tissue and Organ Culture*, 110(1): 23–33.
- xviii Wu, Q.S., Y.N. Zou and E.F. Abd_Allah. 2014. Mycorrhizal Association and ROS in Plants. In: P. Ahmad (Ed): *Oxidative Damage to Plants*. Elsevier Inc. 453- 475.

Table.1. Effect of salt and ascorbic acid on physiological parameters of sugarcane plants

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*(Pooled mean of two plant crops)

Treat Ments	Germination percentage at 35 DAP		Tiller population ('000/ha)		Millable cane population ('000/ha)		Plant height (cm)		Number of nodes per plant		Length of internodes (cm)	
	Plant crop I	Plant crop II	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop
T ₁	68	69	125.67	126.67	116.90	117.65	309	311	19	18	6.17	6.24
T ₂	71	72	131.33	135.25	120.78	122.09	318	323	20	21	7.79	7.61
T ₃	83	85	142.48	145.06	129.88	131.18	356	358	25	24	10.11	10.32
T ₄	70	72	135.48	141.24	126.76	123.89	337	348	24	22	8.70	9.08
CD P=(0.05)	NS	NS	4.65	3.97	1.99	1.87	11.12	10.45	2.24	1.65	0.64	0.71

T₁ –Control

T₂ –Foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP

T₃–Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th days after planting

T₄– Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l

Table.2. Effect of ascorbic acid on physiological parameters of sugarcane under salinity

*(Pooled mean of two plant crops)

Treatments	Leaf Area (cm ²)		Leaf Area Index		Total chlorophyll content (mg/g)		Proline content (µg/g of tissue)	
	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop
T ₁	560.56	562.68	3.11	3.13	1.752	1.753	288	290
T ₂	650.45	658.24	3.48	3.51	1.932	1.925	311	309
T ₃	727.90	737.15	3.85	3.88	2.273	2.265	325	320
T ₄	694.05	700.54	3.69	3.79	2.112	2.157	319	315
CD P=(0.05)	21.68	20.94	0.15	0.10	0.074	0.058	15.01	14.89

T₁ –Control

T₂ –Foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP

T₃–Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th days after planting

T₄– Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l

Table.3. Fig 3 Effect of ascorbic acid on yield parameters of sugarcane under salinity condition

Treat Ments	Cane Length (cm)		Cane Girth (cm)		Cane Yield (t/ha)		Sugar Yield (t/ha)		CCS%	
	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop
T ₁	161.21	165.20	2.12	2.20	101.6	105.02	11.19	11.24	10.97	10.96
T ₂	172.23	176.80	2.30	2.38	109.6	110.62	12.28	12.33	11.13	11.25
T ₃	202.42	204.20	2.70	2.72	124.6	125.71	14.04	14.12	11.32	11.36
T ₄	180.15	197.60	2.30	2.52	114.2	116.96	13.42	13.64	11.24	11.21
CD P=(0.05)	11.10	14.11	0.28	0.23	3.39	7.24	0.44	0.32	0.24	0.23

*(Pooled mean of two plant crops)

T₁ –Control

T₂ –Foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP

T₃–Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th days after planting

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T₄– Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l

Table.1. Effect of ascorbic acid on economics of sugarcane under salinity condition

Treat Ments	Cost of Cultivation (Rs.)		Gross income (Rs.)		Net income (Rs.)		B:C ratio	
	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop	Plant crop*	Ratoon crop
T ₁	177320	177320	288137	297780	110817	120460	1.62	1.67
T ₂	178470	178470	310825	313662	132355	135192	1.74	1.76
T ₃	179850	179850	353365	356485	173850	176635	1.96	1.98
T ₄	178700	178700	323871	331528	145171	152828	1.81	1.86

*(Pooled mean of two plant crops)

T₁ –Control

T₂ –Foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th DAP

T₃–Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l + foliar spray of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l at 45th days after planting

T₄– Sett treatment of ascorbic acid with 0.2g/l